

THE ROLE OF MNEMONOTECHNICS AS A MODERN METHODOLOGY

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In modern life, children receive a huge amount of information. Children use smartphones, tablets and computers very well. But taking in a lot of information is not always the right solution to keep the necessary knowledge in memory. It is desirable to raise children with immunity to timely information. The mnemonic method is very useful for developing memory in children and developing their ability to remember. Having a good memory creates a foundation for a child to easily absorb knowledge and receive news quickly. How does the mnemonic method affect a child's development?

Memory, attention, ability to imagine develops, speech develops, vocabulary increases, Their perception of the environment expands.

Mental and emotional development increases. During the application of the mnemonic method, it is possible to find aspects such as shyness in children, inability to join their peers.

Mnemonic technics mean that two hemispheres of the brain work simultaneously.

Creativity is formed in children. In fact, the development of memory is influenced by several internal and external factors, such as sleep, food, family environment. In the method of mnemonics, the child remembers figuratively.

"Visual recall"

For example, a picture of a ship is pasted on his locker at a preschool. Now he realizes that the mastrobe in the picture of the ship belongs to him, and the clothes and shoes in it are also his. Even though he doesn't know how to read, he stays in front of the shelf with a picture of a ship and takes what he needs. "Make it yourself"

Another interesting method. The child is shown four unrelated pictures arranged in a square shape. The picture in each square represents one word. Based on the images, the child should draw a picture. "Chair". The essence of this memorization technique is to associate images with each other. The teacher shows the children 4 logically connected pictures and then covers them. Children should recall the story without making any mistakes about what is depicted in the pictures.

"Professions" The teacher shows photos of 4 professions. Then he asks who feeds people. Children answer his questions. In turn, the educators ask questions such as who sews clothes, who teaches children, and who guards them.

"Compare" The teacher shows a picture of two kittens. Children should find and analyze their similarities and differences. For example, one kitten's mother is brown and meows loudly, and the other kitten is her child. He meows softly. His size is smaller than his mother's.

